

Long-Term Degradation of Concrete Fracture Toughness under Exposure to Aggressive Chloride Environments

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Abstract

This paper presents the outcome of a long-term experimental study aimed at the effect of chloride attack on the concrete body, and its influence on the fracture performance. Fracture tests involved Brazilian discs with central notch (BDCN) made from concrete with blended cement as a binder. The BDCN samples were placed into a 50% saturated sodium chloride solution (NaCl). Two initial conditions of porous space were considered, i.e., empty (air filled), and water-saturated. SEM observations are presented to discuss the hydration products as well as to study the damage to the microstructure. Additionally, the EDS analysis was employed to understand the origin of both hydration and corrosion products. The exposure to chlorides significantly, up to 26 %, reduces the fracture toughness K_{IC} depending on the exposure time and initial conditions of pore space. The concept of effective thickness B_{eff} that links microstructural degradation with macroscopic fracture behaviour was introduced.

Keywords: Fracture toughness; Chlorides; BDCN; Blended cement;

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Highlights

- A long-term study of chloride-induced degradation in concrete fracture behaviour.
- Pore saturation conditions (air-filled vs. water-saturated) influence chloride ingress.
- Friedel's salt formation linked to chemical corrosion of cement matrix.
- Fracture toughness K_{IC} measured over 360 days of exposure.
- K_{IC} decreases with exposure time and saturation conditions.
- Effective thickness B_{eff} proposed to simulate a time-dependent degradation.

Abbreviations

BDCN	Brazilian disc with central notch	SIF	stress intensity factor
OPC	ordinary Portland cement	CM	colorimetric method
GBFS	granulated blast furnace slag	CPD	cylinder for penetration depth
EDS	energy dispersive spectroscopy	CMOD	crack mouth opening displacement
SEM	scanning electron microscopy		

Nomenclature

a, b	fitting parameters [mm]	F_{\max}	maximum measured force [kN]
D	specimen's diameter [mm]	$Y_{I,BDCN}(a/R, \alpha)$	geometry shape function [-]
B	specimen's thickness [mm]	a/R	relative notch length [-]
B_{eff}	effective thickness [mm]	L	specimen's length [mm]
a	crack length [mm]	h_{Cl}	chloride penetration depth [mm]
α	notch inclination angle [°]	$h_{Cl,uni}$	unified chloride penetration depth [mm]
K_I	stress intensity factor for mode I	t	age [days]
K_{IC}	fracture toughness [MPamm ^{1/2}]	t_{Cl}	chloride exposure time [days]
$K_{IC}^{Cl^-}$	chloride saturated fracture toughness [MPamm ^{1/2}]	δ	measured displacement [mm]
		r^2	coefficient of determination [-]
		H_{cyl}	cylinder's height [mm]

1. Introduction

Throughout its service lifetime, a concrete structure is exposed to various environmental conditions that can affect its long-term durability. Such environmental conditions are reflected in the normative documents leading to increasing the protective cover layer or reducing the permeability by mixture composition adjustments [1]. Chloride penetration, primarily caused by marine environments or de-icing salts [2] has been recognised to belong among the major contributing factors to structural damage of concrete. As a result, the durability of concrete structures has remained a critical concern for both scientific community [3–5] and standardisation bodies [6–8] for decades.

Generally speaking, there are two major issues with the chloride environment on reinforced concrete, particularly on its steel reinforcement [2,9]. First, is the attack on steel reinforcement accompanied by cracking and spalling of the concrete protective cover layer, as the products of steel corrosion occupy a larger volume than the original steel bars. The second consequence, which goes hand in hand with the damage to the cover layer, is the reduction of the cross-sectional area of the steel-reinforcement bars, resulting in the reduction of its load-carrying capacity. Whereas the first problem is typically observable on the surface of the concrete structural part, the second one has a highly localised form of pitting corrosion on the steel bar [10].

Besides the steel corrosion process caused by chloride exposure, cement matrix itself can also undergo chemical degradation. Based on studies in the literature, we can generally distinguish between three types of chemical corrosion of cement matrix when exposed to liquid environment: leaching of calcium hydroxide; substitutive reactions of aggressive environment; and volumetric changes due to chemical reactions [11]. The above-mentioned three types of concrete chemical corrosion are defined in [12] and described in Figure 1. Type I and Type II chemical corruptions are either causing alkalinity loss, or the increase of porosity and permeability and/or carbonation. On the other hand, Type III corrosion does not affect either strength or porosity, as it is the result of chemical reactions with their products having

a higher volume, leading directly to the damage of the microstructure. Furthermore, Type III chemical corrosion is often neglected.

Figure 1: Chemical corrosion of cement matrix exposed to liquid environments adopted from [12].

As the reduction of CO₂ emissions is the centre of attention of environmental policies, the cement industry is motivated to significantly lower its production by 2050 [13]. Hence, material science started reducing the amount of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) by using the blended cement systems, which usually combine pozzolanic materials or industrial by-products with OPC. Such mineral admixtures or by-products such as fly-ash, limestone or granulated blast furnace slag (GBFS) have been studied with respect to mechanical as well as durability performance worldwide [14]. In total, up to 64 % of OPC could be replaced [15]. Hence, the understanding of the chemical corrosion of new binders is important to increase their wide applicability.

The assessment of chloride penetration depth [16] is crucial for the evaluation of the remaining structures' lives [17–19] and a further consideration of maintenance and renovation strategies. However, most of the vast amount of research is devoted to the evaluation of the effect of chlorides on the corrosion-induced structural problems. Even though the effect of chloride ingress on the concrete pore structure has been evaluated [20,21], its effect on the fracture parameters is not frequently studied. Therefore, although there have been initial attempts [22,23], the effect of the chloride ingress and crystallization on fracture properties deserves further attention due to an insufficient understanding of the mechanisms by which chloride ingress affects the fracture properties of the concrete matrix.

Furthermore, it is important to identify the damage mechanisms in the microstructure, which are later emerging in macro damage as a reduction in both mechanical fracture and mechanical properties [24,25]. Fracture properties are useful when performing either a non-linear structural analysis [26,27] or fatigue damage evaluation analysis [28]. To perform structural analysis, one needs to implement material models which typically use fracture energy G_F as an input [29], while the fatigue damage assessment is done employing the stress intensity factor (SIF) and its critical value K_{IC} – fracture toughness [30,31].

Previous studies have attempted to relate concrete fracture behaviour to chloride exposure, often indirectly, for example by using electrical resistance-based approaches to monitor crack development and permeability changes [32–34]. Experimental investigations have primarily focused on the influence of cracking on transport properties, such as gas, water, and chloride permeability, using split-cylinder or similar tests [35–38]. These findings have been widely utilised in numerical models addressing coupled transport and mechanical processes in cracked concrete [39–42]. However, despite the extensive body of work on chloride transport and corrosion-induced damage, the direct effect of chloride ingress on the fracture mechanics properties of the concrete matrix itself remains insufficiently understood,

particularly in terms of long-term degradation of fracture toughness. Only a limited number of studies have explicitly addressed fracture behaviour under chloride exposure [22,43].

Highlighting a clear research gap that the present study aims to address, this paper presents the results of a long-term experimental study and shows the direct connection between chloride attack and the reduction of the material's fracture toughness K_{IC} . For this purpose, we employed an accelerated chloride ingress to the concrete body using 50% saturated sodium chloride (NaCl) solution according to NT Build 443 [44]. Fracture tests were performed on concrete Brazilian disk with central notch (BDCN) samples made with cement CEM II, comprising of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) blended with granulated blast furnace slag (GBFS) as a binder, with the thickness of approximately 30 mm. Additionally, two different initial pore saturation conditions were investigated before placing BDCN into the NaCl solution – air-filled and water saturated. To capture the chloride ingress to the concrete body, chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} was measured at various times. The macroscale mechanical experiments were accompanied by the microstructure analysis aiming at the hydration products observations, and to microstructural damage detection. The experimental results show progressive damage to the microstructure influencing both mechanical strengths and fracture toughness K_{IC} . Based on the experimental results, a concept of effective thickness is proposed, offering a time-dependent prediction of material degradation of concrete exposed to chloride environments.

2. Material and Experimental Details

In what follows, we present a concrete mixture composition together with measured properties of fresh and hardened concrete. Afterwards, the fracture test setup, the testing equipment, and the concrete samples employed for the material's fracture toughness K_{IC} assessment are presented. This is followed by the introduction of environmental conditions and chloride penetration depth measurement techniques. Lastly, we briefly introduce the equipment for microstructural analysis using SEM and EDS. The selection of these methods provides for a comprehensive analysis of the complex phenomenon of chloride ingress to concrete body, and helps to quantify the observed degradation of the material's properties.

2.1 Mixture Composition

In this experimental study, a blended cement CEM II/A-S 42R was selected as a binder. This binder consists of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) and granulated blast furnace slag (GBFS) in the ratio of 8/2. The cement was mixed with aggregates consisting of natural 0/4 mm sand and crushed granite with two fraction sizes of 4/8 and 8/16 mm. To achieve good workability, polycarboxylate superplasticizer Sika Viscocrete® 4035 (Sika AG, Switzerland) was used. To increase air porosity, a calcium carbonate-based air-entraining admixture SikaControl® AER-200 (Sika AG, Switzerland) was added to the mixture. It was mixed in a batch of 2 m³ in volume and placed into moulds, in which it was left for 3 days and then demoulded. The mixture composition per m³ is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mixture composition per 1 m³.

Cement II/A-S 42.5 R [kg]	Fine aggregate 0/4 mm [kg]	Coarse aggregate 4/8 mm [kg]	Coarse aggregate 8/16 mm [kg]	Viscocrete® 4035 [kg]	SikaControl® AER-200 [kg]	Water [kg]
400	752	204	755	2.8	0.5	165

Table 1 presents a mixture composition characterised by water to cement ratio w/c of 0.4215, which could be placed into standard plain concrete types. Additionally, this mixture could be characterised by the standard definition of concrete grade as C 30/37 XF4.

Prior to sample preparation, the basic properties of fresh concrete were obtained, whereas mechanical strengths/properties were tested in hardened state at the 28 days age. Fresh properties indicate good concrete workability. Both fresh and hardened properties were determined according to European EN and international ISO standards with the results presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Properties of fresh and hardened concrete, and long-term compressive strength $f_c(\text{age})$ development.

Properties of fresh concrete:			
Volume density ρ [kg/m ³]	Air content [%]	Slump test [mm]	Flow table test [mm]
2 280	5.5	220	590
Properties of hardened concrete:			
Volume density ρ [kg/m ³]	Flexural strength f_{cf} [MPa]	Young's modulus E_c [GPa]	Water penetration depth h_w [mm]
2 310 ± 5	6.6 ± 0.2	30.8 ± 1.11	11 ± 2.1
Compressive strength $f_c(\text{age})$ [MPa] – cube 150 mm			
28 days	90 days	270 days	450 days
56.9 ± 0.35	64.6 ± 1.13	66.1 ± 0.68	74.4 ± 2.42

As presented in Table 2, mechanical properties were tested at the 28 days age, while a special attention was paid to the compressive strength f_c , which was tested at various ages of 28, 90, 270 and 450 days, and the long-term development of compressive strength f_c was obtained, as it helps to correlate the mechanical behaviour with fracture properties. The compressive strength increased by approx. 30 % when comparing the standard testing age of 28 days with the 450 days age. This observed increase in compressive strength f_c is due to the continuous storage of test samples in water environment providing sufficient water for proper cement hydration.

In addition to mechanical properties obtained at hardened state, the water penetration depth d_w was measured according to European standards, which use a water pressure of 0.5 MPa for 72 hours. The obtained water penetration depth h_w was 11 mm. As presented in Table 2, the measured mechanical parameters – compressive strength f_c – satisfy the classification of the utilized concrete according to the normative document with a minimum class of C 30/37.

2.2 Fracture Test Setup

The BDCN test sample was selected for fracture tests, as it provides information on the fracture under various loading conditions while using less concrete material for sample preparation. Another advantage is that the test is performed under relatively simple loading conditions using compressive force. BDCN samples were created using standardised cylinders with a height H_{cyl} of 300 mm and a diameter D of 150 mm for compressive strength testing by cutting them into discs with a thickness B of approximately 30 mm. The initial notch was made using a water jet cutter with a length a of 60 mm. The water jet cutting allows for precise notch preparation and provides notch through the disc's thickness.

The example of a BDCN sample is shown in Figure 2(a). Fracture tests were performed using an electro-mechanical testing rig with a capacity of 250 kN with an error of 0.2 % (LABORTECH, Czech Republic) with built-in strain gage force transducer (AST, Germany) used for loading force measurement. A loading rate of 0.02 mm/min was used for all the tested samples. The experimental test setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overall view of the BDCN test setup, and BDCN with a detail on the notch.

As it can be seen in Figure 2, we used two linear variable differential transducers (LVDT) with a measurement range of 2 mm and an error of $\pm 1\%$ (Precisor Messtechnik, Germany) for measuring the induced displacement of the upper support. These two transducers are placed in a diagonal position to obtain the mean value representing the displacement at the center of the loading platen. Additionally, the CMOD values were measured using a clip gauge (FCE BUT, Czech Republic) with a measurement range of 4 mm and an error of $\pm 1\%$. All the measured values were acquired with the use of a universal eight-channel measuring amplifier (HBK, Germany).

Measuring the maximum force F_{max} during the experiment on the BDCN sample allows for measuring the material's fracture toughness for mode I K_{IC} . The fracture toughness can be calculated as follows [45]:

$$K_{IC} = \frac{F_{max}\sqrt{a}}{RB\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{a}{R}}} Y_{I,BDCN}(a/R, \alpha_n), \quad (1)$$

where F_{max} is the maximum measured force, a is the crack/notch length, and $Y_{I,BDCN}(a/R, \alpha)$ is the geometry shape function dependent on the relative notch ratio of a/R and the notch inclination angle α . R and B are the disc's radius and thickness, respectively. The geometry function $Y_{I,BDCN}(a/R, \alpha)$, in this case of $a/R = 0.4$ and $\alpha = 0^\circ$, has a value of 0.964 [46].

2.3 Environmental Conditions

In this study, two chloride exposure situations were investigated alongside a reference water environment, resulting in three sets of test specimens. After demoulding, the concrete samples were initially air-cured outside laboratory conditions. Subsequently, the disc-like samples (BDCN) and cylinders were stored in a liquid environment – either in tap water or in a sodium chloride (NaCl) solution. The chloride exposure environment consisted of a plastic tank filled with a sodium chloride solution at a concentration of 2.62 mol/L (equivalent to 16.5 g NaCl per 100 g of water). This corresponds to approximately 50% saturation, according to the NordTest [44] method. The solution was replaced monthly, and the total volume was adjusted according to the number of samples to maintain a consistent free surface area per specimen.

This relatively high chloride concentration was chosen to accelerate chloride ingress, and thus reduce the required experimental duration. An overview of the concrete samples stored in the chloride tank is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Stored concrete samples in 50% saturated NaCl solution.

As can be seen in Figure 3, the concrete samples were stored in the tanks with sufficient spacing to ensure a uniform chloride penetration across all specimens. The figure shows two different sample geometries: Brazilian disc with central notch (BDCN) and cylindrical specimens. The cylindrical

samples were used specifically for measuring the chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} and will be referred to hereafter as cylinders for penetration depth (CPD) measurements.

The concrete specimens were tested after various chloride exposure times (t_{Cl}) to assess the potential material degradation caused by chloride ingress. To capture the long-term degradation behaviour under aggressive environmental conditions, exposure durations equivalent to 28, 56, 90, 180, and 360 days were selected to capture the evolution of degradation mechanisms. These correspond to different stages of service life in accelerated laboratory conditions.

For easier orientation in the experimental results, the following labels will be used: R0 are the reference concrete samples stored outside aggressive environmental conditions, while concrete samples stored in aggressive environment will be referred to as S28 and S90. More specifically, S28 samples were placed into the chloride solution at an age of 28 days, after initial air curing, while S90 samples were first air-cured for 28 days, then water-cured, and, at the age of 90 days, they were placed into the chloride solution. These curing conditions were selected for the assessment of the chloride phase delay in material degradation. To better illustrate the use of different storage periods of concrete samples under different environmental conditions, a timeline of fracture tests is presented in Figure 4.

TIMELINE:

Figure 4: Timeline of fracture test and environmental conditions.

The timeline as presented in Figure 4 distinguishes between the total specimen age t and the chloride exposure time t_{Cl} . The timeline indicates all curing conditions, i.e., air-cured, water-cured and chloride exposure. All samples were air-cured for 28 days. R0 samples were water-cured after the initial period of air-curing, S28 samples were placed directly into the NaCl solution, and finally S90 samples were air-cured for 28 days, then water-cured for 62 days. After treatment in a non-aggressive environment at the age of $t = 90$ days, S90 samples were placed in the NaCl solution. Reference samples R0 were tested at the same age as S28 and S90 samples to track the long-term development of fracture properties over time.

2.4 Chloride Penetration Depth

To analyse the influence of chloride ingress on the degradation of the mechanical and fracture properties of concrete, the assessment of the chloride penetration depth is crucial. For this purpose, we selected two evaluation methods using experimental data. The first one is using analytical methods to obtain the chemical composition of concrete as well as the concentration of chloride ions. The other one is the colorimetric method (CM) using chemical reaction of silver nitrate $AgNO_3$ with chloride ions on the damaged ligament according to NordTEST [44].

To evaluate the chloride depth h_{Cl} , we exposed a cylindrical sample with only two surfaces (bottom and top) to an aggressive chloride environment. The other surfaces of such samples were covered with epoxy, which is sealed and prevents the ingress of Cl^- ions to the concrete body. In this way, the chloride ions Cl^- penetration direction could be interpreted as one-dimensional. The preparation of a concrete sample and the illustration of the one-dimensional chloride penetration are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Concrete sample for analytical assessment of chloride penetration depth.

Figure 5 presents the geometry and dimensions of the concrete sample, which is slightly different from the BDCN geometry. In the case of chloride penetration, the discs have a diameter D of 104 mm and thickness B of approx. 60 mm. The discs were made by cutting the cylinder in such a way that the disc had a surface with exposed aggregates, which simulates the BDCN sample as closely as possible. The thickness of 60 mm was selected based on the long-term nature of this experimental study; while using a thinner disc, the chloride ions would penetrate through the whole thickness.

Subsequently, Figure 5 shows the location of each layer in which the presence of chloride ions was determined. Each layer, as presented in Figure 5, was carefully sanded at the thickness of 1.5 mm from the bulk material. Then the material (dust) collected from each layer was analysed for the chloride ion Cl^- content in bulk material. The material was analysed at a total thickness h_{tot} of 11.5 mm (measured from the free surface) within the age of 56 and 180 days. At 360 days of age the total thickness h_{tot} was extended to 20 mm. A weighed portion of finely ground concrete was leached in distilled water. The suspension was heated and stirred with a magnetic stirrer for 30 minutes. Afterwards, the suspension was filtered using a paper filter, and the chloride content in the leachate was determined by mercurimetric titration. The equivalence point was indicated by a mixed indicator (diphenylcarbazone and bromophenol blue) after acidification of the solution by a change in colour from yellow to purple. The chloride content was calculated based on the consumption of the volumetric solution expressed as a percentage of the total weight of the concrete.

The CM method is performed post-test, following the procedure described by NordTEST [44], by spraying the chloride-contaminated specimens with AgNO_3 solution on the ligament of the CPD samples. Then the chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} is measured at points from the free surface with an equidistant distance of approx. 10 mm. Thus, the value of chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} is the average value of the depths in 10 measurements. The damaged sample example used in the CM analysis is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Ligament of the damaged sample - (a) original photograph and (b) contrast-adjusted photograph with marked identified chloride front.

As can be seen in Figure 6, the use of silver nitrate reacts with the chloride-contaminated cement paste and creates a reaction product that is white in colour compared to the bulk material. The boundary between the reaction product and the cement paste can be interpreted as the chloride penetration depth

h_{Cl} or the chloride front. Subsequently, Figure 6(b) shows a contrast-adjusted photo that was used in the evaluation of chloride penetration depth, as it helps to identify the chloride front with more precision.

When both methods are compared, the first provides more precise results using relatively complicated experimental instruments, while the CM method is based on a relatively simple application of a liquid solution of silver nitrate $AgNO_3$, and provides rather informative results of the chloride front. Nonetheless, both methods are suitable to meet the objectives set in this study and are well-recognised among the researchers who deal with this topic.

2.5 Microstructure Analysis

In this work, we performed a microstructure observation using Mira3 Tescan SEM (Tescan, Czech Republic) on aged specimens. SEM analysis was used for the assessment of cement hydration products and for the analysis of the chloride reaction with hydration products. Then energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was used to assess the elemental content within the hardened concrete sample. In total, two samples were analysed after total exposure to chloride for 365 days and one reference sample stored in water for the same age.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the experimental results, including chloride penetration depth, microstructural observations, and fracture toughness K_{IC} at different exposure ages. Based on these results, an effective thickness B_{eff} , as a function of exposure time and chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} , is introduced to account for chloride ingress is introduced.

3.1 Chloride Penetration Depth

Keeping in mind the main goal of this study, the analysis of long-term effects of chloride ions Cl^- on the fracture toughness K_{IC} of the studied concrete, the chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} has to be measured at various chloride exposure ages t_{Cl} to capture the rate of ingress of chloride into the concrete body and to quantify the degradation rate of the material. The presence of chloride ions was assessed by the colorimetric method at the 28-, 56-, 90-, 180- and 360-day age as well as by the measurement of the chloride ions Cl^- concentration at various depths. The evaluation of the chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} was performed by the colorimetric method for both S28 and S90 samples, and the results are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Chloride penetration depth measured by colorimetric method including fitting parameters.

The measured chloride penetration depths h_{Cl} as presented in Figure 7 agree with the general expectations, as S28 samples show higher chloride concentration values than S90 samples. The difference between S28 and S90 could be attributed to S90's pores (air voids) having been fully saturated with water, in which diffusion of Cl^- ions takes place, while the water from pores in S28 samples dried out. Saturated pores with water led to chloride ingress due to the effect of chloride solution diffusion

mainly in the case of S90 samples. On the other hand, S28 samples show accelerated chloride ingress to the concrete body as the pores were left empty (filled with air) when placing the test samples into the chloride solution. Hence, the migration of chloride ions via saturation takes place, driven also by the hydraulic pressure gradient and capillary suction. The chloride penetration difference is indicated by higher initial penetration depth h_{Cl} , as saturation is a more accelerated process compared to diffusion.

Additionally, the maximum measured chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} is 16.5 mm for S28 samples at the exposure time t_{Cl} of 360 days, while for S90 samples the measured chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} is 14 mm at the same exposure age t_{Cl} . Both values, when transformed from CPD to BDCN geometry, indicate that the chloride Cl^- ions front would reach the centre of the BDCN samples as the thickness B of the disc is approximately 28 to 30 mm. It is worth noting that the samples are exposed from both sides. Therefore, the penetration front passes all the way through the thickness of the BDCN sample. It is worth mentioning that the chloride Cl^- ions concentration within the area of the samples is higher than that of the chloride front. The chloride concentration increases from the chloride front to the exposed surface.

Unfortunately, the colorimetric method for the assessment of chloride penetration depth serves primarily as an initial evaluation method as it does not provide exact information on the chloride ions Cl^- concentration at the chloride front. Therefore, we complement this method with the chloride profile analysis of saturated concrete with chloride ions Cl^- content. 3 different ages of both S28 and S90 samples were analysed by this method. The results of the analytical method are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Measured chloride Cl^- ions concentration at different chloride exposure ages t_{Cl} .

The results presented in Figure 8 show the chloride ions Cl^- concentration measured at $t_{Cl} = 56, 180$ and 360 days of penetration age, respectively. A careful observation of Figure 8 reveals a different chloride ingress rate at $t_{Cl} = 56$ days when comparing S28 and S90 curves (blue curves). At later age, the chloride profiles show similar trends as in the study of Weerdt et al. [47] for both S28 and S90 samples. An interesting result can be observed in Figure 8 for 180 days, as both curves are approaching the chloride ions concentration value of 0.2% at the depth of 10.5 mm. Moreover, the identical chloride ions concentration was measured for sample S28 at t_{Cl} of 56 days. This intersection point demonstrates no difference in the initial conditions as the profiles collide at one point. We relate this difference in ingress rate to different porous space environmental conditions; in S28 samples, penetration takes place first through capillary suction and saturation of empty voids, and later on by diffusion due to empty (air filled) pores, while in S90 samples only diffusion occurs. Saturation is a much faster process than diffusion of pores.

According to Weerdt [48], chloride ion concentrations higher than 0.6% indicate strongly bound chlorides, which are associated with AFm hydration products. When exposed to a chloride environment for prolonged periods, AFm phases can transform into expansive chloroaluminate phases, such as Kuzel's or Friedel's salt [49]. The study of Florea and Brouwers [50] documents that the amount of bound chlorides depends on external concentration and type of concrete. The higher the concentration of

chlorides the higher the amount of bond chlorides. E.g. for concentration of 46 % used here in according to [44], there is 0.9 to 1.6 % of chlorides per concrete mass bonded depending on studied HPC concrete. Therefore, the amount of bonded chlorides increases with time and depth following the measured chloride ions Cl^- concentration as presented in Figure 8. It is worth noting that Figure 8 represents a one-dimensional ingress, which would be hard to achieve in structural application. However, it provides valuable information on the rate and depth of chloride ions presence in a concrete body with implications to the structural design related to the depth of the affected zone.

3.2 Microstructure Analysis

Microstructure analysis was performed at $t_{\text{Cl}} = 360$ days of exposure age to chloride environment. The samples were analysed at the centre of the cross-sections of the CPD cylindrical concrete samples made for analytical chloride penetration depth evaluation (see Figure 5). The most representative examples of microstructure obtained from SEM images of R0, S28, and S90 microstructures are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Microstructure observations obtained by SEM at the chloride exposure of 360 days age – (a) reference R0 sample, (b) S28 sample, and (c) S90 sample.

Figure 9 shows hydration products of all the tested samples at chloride exposure age t_{Cl} of 360 days and verifies the proper hydration of cement in the mixture. The hydration products, Portlandite, AFm, Ettringite and C-S-H gels are present in R0, S28, and S90 samples. Such microstructure indicates proper curing of concrete leading to the expected values of mechanical properties, e.g., compressive strength and Young's modulus. In the case of S28 samples, microstructure observations revealed that the hydration products are present in a lesser extent than in S90 samples, as S90 samples were cured in water for 62 days – longer than S28 samples. This, again, agrees with the general expectation that S90 samples should have more hydration products than S28 samples. Similar observations of denser microstructure and higher amount of hydration products, mainly C-S-H gel, were found in following studies [51–53], where the authors use same cement type and quantify the hydration products by TGA. The denser micro-structure of S90 samples confirms the lower chloride penetration rate as observed in Figure 8.

However, the EDS analysis revealed the presence of chloroaluminate. The presence of chloroaluminate could be linked to the long-term effects of chloride ions diffusion and the consequent chemical reaction with AFm. The long-term exposure to chloride environment changes AFm to Kuzel's salt as the monosulfate is exchanged with chloride and later it will change to Friedel's [54]. The presence of chloroaluminate in microstructure leads to significant damage of a concrete microstructure. Hence, it can have serious consequences on the load-bearing capacity and structural lifetime due to a weaker concrete cover. The EDS analyses of both S28 and S90 samples are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Figure 10: EDS elemental maps obtained on S28 sample at 360 days of chloride exposure age t_{Cl} .

The results of EDS analysis of S28 sample as presented in Figure 10 revealed the presence of chloride penetration to the material's microstructure. When comparing the aluminium elemental map (Figure 10, second figure from the right), the most excessive chloride presence is observed in the locations with the presence of aluminium. Such observations confirm the presence of chloride aluminate, which is often referred to as Kuzel's salt [49,55] and later to Friedel's salt [56].

Figure 11: EDS elemental maps obtained on S90 sample at 360 days of chloride exposure age t_{Cl} .

A similar observation can be made from Figure 11 for S90 samples showing the presence of chloride aluminate in the microstructure. In the case of S90, the chloride presence is not as significant when compared to the observation made from S28 samples. This difference can be related to the empty pores when placing S28 sample into the NaCl solution, in which chloride ions migration led to an accelerated chloride penetration depth and resulted in chemical corrosion of cement hydration products.

Similarly to hydration products, EDS analysis as presented in Figure 10 and Figure 11 revealed a higher Cl⁻ ions content in S28 samples when compared to S90 EDS results.

Furthermore, the chloride presence is mainly in the locations with the presence of hydration products containing aluminium, which, again, confirms the assumption of formation of chloroaluminate – Friedel's salt – due to a long-term exposure to an aggressive environment. This observation could be seen in both S28 and S90 samples. Additionally, the formation of chloroaluminate could be attributed to the presence of aluminium in GBFS, which was not investigated [9].

GBFS present in blended OPC CEM II A/S contributes to the formation of C-S-H gel because it supports the reactions leading to its formation. GBFS has two amorphous phases; the first reacts to create C-S-H gel, while the second remains in the crystalline phase. GBFS itself could contain calcium aluminates, which are responsible for the formation of chloroaluminate to a greater extent than pure OPC CEM I [57].

The formation of secondary ettringite is due to sulphur exposure, which was not present during the experiments. We can also neglect the alkali-silica reaction of aggregates, for which the presence of amorphous SiO₂ is necessary. Granite aggregates do not contain amorphous SiO₂.

3.3 Fracture Behaviour and Fracture Toughness

Fracture behaviour is typically documented by recording a load-displacement (F - δ) diagram during the experiment, which in the case of BDCN sample does not provide as valuable information as for the other geometries used for fracture testing due to a rather brittle behaviour. BDCN often splits due to the accumulated energy leading to a sample's complete destruction. Therefore, load-CMOD (F -CMOD) diagrams are used in the fracture process characterisation, as they provide a $CMOD_{max}$ value corresponding to the maximum measured load F_{max} . More information is obtained this way, as it can be directly compared with the analytical formulas for the calculation of CMOD available in the literature [45]. The recorded F -CMOD diagrams obtained from BDCN fracture tests of all the tested samples are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12 gives a comprehensive overview of the measured F -CMOD diagrams, in which the scatter of results is represented by mean values, minimum and maximum forces, which are highlighted in blue and red, respectively. This form of presentation of the results provides a full insight into the experimental testing as well as it provides valuable information on the heterogeneous behaviour of concrete. From the material's resistance and mechanical performance viewpoint, the results presented in Figure 12 show a significant reduction in load-bearing capacity, i.e., the maximum measured force F_{max} , mainly for S28 and S90 samples, which is declining with the increasing chloride exposure time t_{Cl} , and this decrease is more pronounced at the t_{Cl} of 360 days. The overall reduction of mechanical performance can be noticed from stiffness loss, which is evident in the increase of the CMOD value at a later age. This observation made from F -CMOD experimental records fully supports the microstructural observations, which detected the presence of the chloride aluminate in cement hydration products.

Figure 12: Recorded F -CMOD diagrams - a) R0, b) S28, and c) S90 samples at various age t and chloride exposure time t_{CI} .

The fracture behaviour in the case of the reference R0 sample is oscillating with the increasing trend during the first half-year of the experiments. The results have stabilized after 180 days of age with a slightly decreasing trend. In the case of S28 sample, the CMOD increases from the beginning until 90 days and then has a decreasing trend. Similarly, an observation of the performance made from S90 samples shows an increasing trend until 180 days after casting, which is then followed with decreasing CMOD in later ages.

The stiffness loss due to chemical corrosion of hydration products is more observable when plotting the $CMOD_{max}$, i.e., at $F = F_{max}$, values along the chloride exposure time t_{Cl} . These $CMOD_{max}$ could be interpreted as a maximum crack opening displacement prior to the specimen's failure and provides useful practical information. The evolution of stiffness reduction in relation to chloride exposure time t_{Cl} is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Stiffness reduction of R0, S28, and S90 samples.

As it can be seen in Figure 13, the measured $CMOD_{max}$ shows a high scatter, which is in agreement with the observation made from the analysis of F -CMOD graphs as presented in Figure 12. Moreover, the S90 results obtained from S90 show a higher stiffness in the interval from $(0, 180)$ days of age, when compared to R0 values. We relate this temporary stiffness increase to rehydration of clinker minerals forming denser micro-structure. The measured values for S28 samples correspond to the general agreement, as such samples overall evince the lowest stiffness values. Moreover, we can observe a significant initial reduction of stiffness in the interval from $(90, 118)$ days of age.

This observed difference of a significant reduction of the mechanical performance is more pronounced when plotting the mean values of fracture toughness K_{IC} measured at different sample age t and chloride exposure time t_{Cl} . The mean values of fracture toughness K_{IC} were obtained from 5 samples tested at various chloride exposure times t_{Cl} using a measured dimension as an input to Eq. (1). The reference samples for both alternatives were kept under the same conditions (see Figure 4). However, the testing of the reference samples R0 was conducted at the same age as for chloride-exposed samples S28 and S90. Therefore, the particular couple of tests are presented separately. The obtained results of mean fracture toughness K_{IC} are presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Long-term development of fracture toughness K_{IC} .

The data presented in Figure 14 indicate a high scatter for all R0, S28, and S90 samples. There is a generally decreasing trend of exposed S28 and S90 samples, with inflection points at the same age as we observed in stiffness reduction, i.e., 90 days and 180 days for S28 and S90 samples, respectively. On the other hand, a slight increase of fracture toughness K_{IC} at the early exposure age due to initial saturation of pores with chlorides can be observed in S28. This initial increase is more pronounced in S90 samples, as they were removed from air and placed into water before being placed into the chloride solution. We link this initial increase to rehydration of unhydrated clinker minerals due to water presence in NaCl solution. However, when the pores start to be saturated with chlorides, the fracture toughness K_{IC} begins to decrease due to the degradation of hydration products. This fracture toughness reduction taking place between 90 and 118 days of age goes simultaneously with stiffness reduction presented via CMOD in Figure 13.

Both S28 and S90 values of K_{IC} show decreasing values. The performance of K_{IC} for S28 went from circa 21 to circa 17, which is 19 percent decrease, while K_{IC} for S90 went from circa 22.5 to circa 20.5, which is 8.8 percent decrease. whereas the reference samples R0 show a slight increase in fracture toughness K_{IC} throughout the experiment. There was observed a scatter in K_{IC} values in the range 200 – 450 days for reference sample R0 at the age of 450 days, which might be the outlier measurement case (see Fig. 14 b). However, the increasing trend is more observable when a least square fitting method is used and the linear function is plotted as the trend indicator. The comparison of the measured fracture toughness K_{IC} values is presented in Figure 15 (a). Overall K_{IC} went from circa 21.5 to 23 circa, which is 6.5 percent increase).

Besides of relative comparison during the exposure time, the relative comparison between reference samples R0 and the exposed samples is shown in Figure 15 (b). The progress of relative fracture toughness K_{IC} shows evident decreasing trend in both S28 (up to 24%) and S90 (up to 11%) at the chloride exposure time $t_{Cl} = 360$ days.

Figure 15: (a) - Comparison of measured fractured toughness K_{IC} of R0, S28, and S90 samples, and (b) - Ratio between K_{IC}^{Cl-} / K_{IC} at various chloride exposure ages t_{Cl} .

The results presented in Figure 15 (a) investigate the degradation of fracture toughness K_{IC} in more detail. The measured fracture toughness K_{IC} for S28 samples is growing only until 90 days of age, whereas the fracture toughness K_{IC} obtained for S90 samples is growing towards 118 days of age. These initial differences in the apparent growth of fracture toughness K_{IC} are related to the amount of the hydration product C_3AH_6 or AFm phases, which firstly contribute to pore filling with strength increase, and then to the formation of such an amount of expansive products that it causes damage of microstructure [48]. S90 samples have a higher content of AFm phases, which corresponds to the effects of placing the sample into water from air, and such environmental conditions contributed to a more profound cement hydration, which is manifested by the increase in fracture toughness K_{IC} . The downtrend or degradation of fracture toughness K_{IC} clearly corresponds to the results obtained from the chloride profiles concentration values, which collided at the same penetration time t_{Cl} of 180 days for both S90 and S28 samples. Moreover, in the case of S28, this concentration was reached at the penetration age of 56 days. Therefore, the fracture toughness reduction K_{IC} starts at the age of 56 days of exposure (90 days of age) in the case of S28, and for exposure time between 90 and 180 days (between 180 and 270 days of age) in the case of S90. This is in agreement with both chloride penetration depth observations (Figure 8) and microstructural characterisation (Figure 9).

However, if the ratio of chloride-saturated fracture toughness K_{IC}^{Cl-} to reference fracture toughness K_{IC} obtained from R0 sample as presented in Figure 15(b) is evaluated, a clear decreasing trend can be observed for both S28 and S90 samples. This clearly indicates that the microstructural changes are already happening from the beginning of the experiment and are increasing with a longer chloride exposure age t_{Cl} . This observation is again supported by the comparison of the penetration depths and shows a correlation of the age of chloride exposition t_{Cl} , as the damaged microstructure cannot carry as much load as properly cured concrete with an appropriately hydrated microstructure with well-known hydration products can.

The result of this study shows a significant load-bearing capacity reduction resulting in lower fracture toughness of concrete. It is worth mentioning that the solution with a concentration of 2.26 molCl/l of NaCl, which we used for accelerated concrete corrosion, would not be present in nature for a long period of time (e.g., seawater contains 0.6-0.7 molCl/l [58]). If such concentrations were present in steel-reinforced concrete, steel corrosion would be the main damaging mechanism to concrete structures. Nonetheless, the formation of chloroaluminate clearly damages the microstructure with a direct influence on macroscale fracture toughness. Moreover, the fully saturated ligament with chloride ions Cl^- represents unique data, as the other studies only considered microstructure partially saturated with chlorides.

3.4 Effective Thickness B_{eff}

The results of fracture toughness K_{IC} clearly document its reduction being dependent on the chloride exposure time t_{Cl} due to the reaction of chlorides with hydration products resulting in damage in the microstructure by a formation of expansive chloraluminite. From the practical point of view, it would be beneficial to provide a general formula for future sample preparation or for the assessment of damage due to the exposure to aggressive environments. Thus, we propose the effective thickness B_{eff} parameter, which is quantitatively expressing the reduction of the load-bearing capacity of a concrete sample placed in an aggressive environment.

For this purpose, we assume the same chloride penetration rate for both S28 and S90 samples, and we introduce the unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ as:

$$h_{\text{Cl,uni}} = h_{\text{Cl}} - b, \quad (2)$$

where h_{Cl} is the chloride penetration depth obtained from CM, and a is the parameter obtained from the curve fitting of the measured chloride penetration depth as presented in Figure 7. The progress of penetration depths for both exposure conditions has a similar trend with linear member of the curve fit parameter a 0.021 for S28 and 0.027 for S90, while the initial value b is different for each of the exposure conditions. The difference is again believed to be caused by the amount of hydration products and the denser microstructure of the S90 sample due to longer water curing. In this way, the penetration of time delay in the chloride between S28 and S90 samples.

By subtracting the fitting constant b , which is equal to 6.19 for S28 and 3.51 for S90, using a simplified linear fit, one can obtain the unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ from the measured penetration depths h_{Cl} . The unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ from the experimental data is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$.

The chloride penetration depth as presented in Figure 16 reveals the same values of chloride penetration depth for both S28 and S90 samples, which is in agreement with the general assumption as both samples were made from the same concrete batch. Furthermore, this observed chloride ingress can serve as a parameter for further analysis of concrete fracture behavior in the presence of aggressive environment. Hence, we propose the effective thickness B_{eff} concept in order to provide a measure of mechanical degradation related to chloride exposure expressed in the theoretical thickness of a sample. B_{eff} parameter can be expressed as follows:

$$B_{\text{eff,increased}} = B + h_{\text{Cl,uni}}, \quad (3)$$

$$B_{\text{eff,reduced}} = B - h_{\text{Cl,uni}}, \quad (4)$$

where B is the sample thickness and $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ is the unified chloride penetration depth. Increased and/or decreased effective thickness B_{eff} are used when analysing the fracture resistance using Eq. (1). If one uses Eq. (1) considering the measured maximum force F_{max} from a sample exposed to aggressive environment, e.g., S28 and S90 with the fracture toughness K_{IC} , one can obtain the effective thickness

$B_{\text{eff,increased}}$, and vice versa. The calculated effective thicknesses B_{eff} using experimental data from R0, S28, and S90 samples are presented in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Effective thickness B_{eff} calculated for various initial conditions (a) - S28 and (b) - S90.

Figure 17 illustrates the calculated effective thickness B_{eff} of concrete specimens subjected to chloride exposure, based on both theoretical and experimental fracture toughness K_{IC} values. The proposed concept of effective thickness B_{eff} allows for the estimation of the mechanical degradation depth induced by chloride ingress by either subtracting or adding the unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ to the nominal sample thickness B . In both Figure 17(a) and Figure 17(b), the blue lines represent the required increase in specimen thickness ($B_{\text{eff,increased}} = B + h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ Eq. (3)) to achieve the fracture toughness K_{IC} of the undamaged reference R0 samples, while the red lines denote the reduction in effective ligament ($B_{\text{eff,reduced}} = B - h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ Eq. (4)) resulting from degradation due to chloride ingress. In other words, the blue lines define the required specimen thickness to preserve the original fracture toughness under aggressive exposure, while the red lines quantify the thickness loss equivalent to the observed performance drop. This dual interpretation makes B_{eff} a valuable design and assessment tool for predicting long-term durability of concrete structures in chloride-rich environments that can be directly linked to chloride exposure depth h_{Cl} . Moreover, the solid lines in Figure 17 correspond to theoretical predictions with the constant F_{max} as an input to Eq. (1), while the dashed lines are based on experimental data using the measured F_{max} and K_{IC} values. The concept of effective thickness B_{eff} thus provides a practical measure of mechanical degradation that can be directly linked to chloride exposure depth h_{Cl} .

The results for S28 samples (Figure 17(a)) exhibit an initial mismatch between the theoretical and experimental effective thickness B_{eff} , which corresponds to the previously observed differences in early-age chloride ingress due to the presence of air-filled pores. These empty pores promote capillary suction and accelerate chloride ingress, resulting in a higher chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} values, and consequently more pronounced reductions in effective thickness B_{eff} . In contrast to this, S90 samples (Figure 17(b)) demonstrate a closer agreement between the predicted and measured effective thickness B_{eff} across all exposure durations t_{Cl} , attributed to the slower and diffusion-controlled chloride transport in water-saturated pores. Overall, the results, as presented in Figure 17, confirm that the unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$ can effectively describe the extent of mechanical deterioration. These results validate the proposed use of B_{eff} as a physically meaningful indicator of chloride-induced degradation and subsequent Friedel's salt formation, linking chloride transport behavior with mechanical performance deterioration.

To further validate the concept of effective thickness B_{eff} as a predictive tool for mechanical performance degradation, the fracture toughness K_{IC} was recalculated using Eq. (1) by substituting different B_{eff} values. This allows for the comparison of theoretical fracture toughness K_{IC} values and experimental

measurements at different chloride exposure times t_{Cl} , while keeping the applied load F constant. Two adjustment scenarios were evaluated: one where $B_{eff,RR}$ gives the thickness of an intact sample with similar performance to a sample with chloride-induced damage ($B - h_{Cl,uni}$), and second where $B_{eff,CI}$ gives the thickness of a sample exposed to chlorides increased ($B + h_{Cl,uni}$) to represent the equivalent undamaged cross-section needed to achieve the same mechanical performance. The results are presented in Figure 18 for both S28 and S90 samples.

Figure 18: Calculated fracture toughness K_{IC} using various effective thicknesses B_{eff} – (a) S28 and (b) S90.

The recalculated fracture toughness K_{IC} using adjusted effective thicknesses dependent on the chloride exposure time t_{Cl} are presented in Figure 18(a) for S28 samples, and in Figure 18(b) for S90 samples. The blue lines represent K_{IC} values calculated for a reduced ligament by $B_{eff, \text{reduced}} = B - h_{Cl, uni}$ at constant load, simulating the degradation of the cross-section. The red lines correspond to $B_{eff, \text{increased}} = B + h_{Cl, uni}$, estimating the fracture toughness K_{IC} - a larger undamaged cross-section would be required to match the exposed sample's performance. Experimental results (green lines) are overlaid for direct comparison. The close agreement between analytical predictions and the experimental data supports the idea that $h_{Cl, uni}$ can reliably quantify the mechanical effects of chloride ingress.

In the case of S28 samples (Figure 18(a)), a strong divergence is observed between the blue and red trends over time, highlighting the more rapid degradation of concrete due to early chloride exposure. The experimental data aligns closely with the theoretical predictions based on reduced B_{eff} , reinforcing the observation that chloride-induced microstructural damage reduces fracture toughness significantly. For S90 samples (Figure 18(b)), the experimental K_{IC} values exhibit a much flatter trend, consistent with slower chloride ingress and delayed degradation due to prolonged water curing. Here, too, the calculated values show a good match, especially at later exposure ages, indicating that the effective thickness approach is equally valid for materials undergoing a slower degradation. Overall, the figure confirms that B_{eff} -based adjustments can serve as a practical and predictive tool for fracture behaviour evaluation in chloride-exposed concrete.

The proposed concept of effective thickness B_{eff} opens the possibility for a time-dependent simulation of fracture toughness K_{IC} in chloride-exposed concrete. By linking B_{eff} to the unified chloride penetration depth $h_{Cl, uni}$, which evolves with exposure time t_{Cl} , a simplified but physically meaningful model can be constructed. Assuming that load F and fracture toughness K_{IC} of the undamaged reference material remain constant, the degradation in K_{IC} over time can be simulated by adjusting B_{eff} according to chloride ingress depth. This framework allows for the estimation of residual fracture performance without performing destructive tests at every time point. Such an approach may prove especially valuable for service-life prediction and durability-based structural design, as it enables the integration of chloride transport models with fracture mechanics formulations. Further refinement could include coupling with

diffusion-based chloride ingress models and incorporating parameters such as porosity, curing quality, and environmental cycles. Nevertheless, the results provide a valuable insight into the long-term deterioration of concrete subjected to chloride environments, showing that chloride ingress affects not only the durability via reinforcement corrosion initiation, but also directly impairs the fracture properties of the concrete matrix. These findings highlight the importance of considering fracture performance in service-life assessments and structural design.

It is important to note that the present study focused on plain concrete samples without steel reinforcement and assumes fully saturated chloride exposure conditions. In practice, the presence of cracks in concrete can significantly accelerate chloride diffusion, acting as preferential pathways for ion ingress. This effect may lead to earlier depassivation of steel reinforcement with a subsequent corrosion initiation and faster degradation of reinforced concrete structures.

Although this study provides a basis for understanding degradation in a controlled environment, further work should explore:

- Reinforced concrete systems, including the role of protective cover layers and the influence of steel corrosion on fracture behaviour;
- Other concrete types, particularly those with supplementary cementitious materials (e.g., fly ash, slag, metakaolin) with different chemical composition which can alter chloride transport, binding mechanisms, and affect the chemical corrosion in concrete and the formation of Friedel's salts in particular;
- Partially saturated exposure conditions, which are more representative of real-world environments;
- Crack-induced chloride ingress to better estimate the onset of corrosion and damage progression in service conditions;
- The effective thickness B_{eff} was calculated using a simplified, unified chloride penetration depth $h_{\text{Cl,uni}}$, which depends on the quality of the concrete microstructure. A more detailed assessment of microstructural quality should therefore be considered in future studies.

These aspects are essential for the broader application of the B_{eff} concept to structural durability design in chloride-laden environments.

The outcomes of this study have potential applications in the design and durability assessment of concrete structures, particularly in bridge engineering and marine infrastructure, where chloride exposure is prevalent. Enhancing fracture-based understanding could contribute to improved structural safety and service-life prediction for critical concrete components.

Conclusions

This experimental study revisited the issue of chemical corrosion in concrete caused by a long-term exposure to long-term chloride-laden environments and introduced a unique fracture mechanics-based approach for damage assessment that capture the time-dependent degradation effect on fracture properties in the studied concrete. The concrete was produced with blended cement incorporating ground granulated blast furnace slag (GBFS).

Fracture behaviour was assessed using the Brazilian disc with central notch (BDCN) geometry. The tests were conducted on samples stored in different environments, categorized as R0 (reference, water), S28 (chloride exposure started at 28 days), and S90 (chloride exposure started at 90 days). Fracture toughness (K_{IC}) was evaluated at chloride exposure durations t_{Cl} of 28, 56, 90, 180, and 360 days. The values of K_{IC} difference at the exposure time 360 days revealed a reduction of up to 24 % for S28 samples and up to 11% for S90 samples, compared to the reference (R0) specimens.

These findings were in-line with observation by localised microstructural analysis using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). SEM indicating revealed a dense and intact microstructure in R0 samples, indicating proper hydration. In contrast, S28 and S90 samples exhibited internal cracking and degradation linked to chemical corrosion. EDS elemental mapping confirmed the presence of chloroaluminate phases, which are known to form expansive products that disrupt the cement matrix. It is worth noting that the SEM and EDS do not cover all the sample size. Therefore, EDS and SEM cannot fully proof that the cracking in case of S28 and S90 is widespread issue throughout the past here in. Nevertheless, authors believes that this is the case.

The study also introduced the concept of effective thickness B_{eff} , derived from the chloride penetration depth, as a physically meaningful parameter that links microstructural degradation with macroscopic fracture behaviour. Recalculated K_{IC} values using B_{eff} matched experimental trends well, supporting its use in predictive modelling. This concept allows for the simulation of time-dependent performance loss and could be integrated into service-life assessment tools for concrete structures exposed to aggressive environments. This approach provides a simplified, yet robust simulation of time-dependent mechanical deterioration, offering a conceptual framework for integrating chloride-induced damage into durability-based structural design and service-life assessment of concrete structures exposed to aggressive environments.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petr Miarka: Visualization, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Dominik Lisztwan:** Methodology. **Dalibor Kocáb:** Methodology. **Patrik Bayer:** Visualization. **Petr Konečný:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

The data used in this study is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16927288>

Appendix A – Experimental Details

In this appendix, we show fitting parameters and derivation of effective thickness B_{eff} . When using least square fitting of the measured chloride penetration depths h_{Cl} data with exponential function $y = a \cdot e^{bt}$, S90 samples exhibit a higher penetration rate than the values obtained from S28 samples. The penetration rate is represented by the parameter b – slope of the exponential curve. The constant a of the fit could be interpreted as penetration depth at time zero, which has no physical/chemical meaning as it should be zero at the time of storage. Both obtained fitting parameters a and b together with the coefficient of determination r^2 are presented in Table 3. **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.**

Table 3: Obtained fitting parameters from both S280 and S90 samples.

sample	a [mm]	b [-]	r^2 [-]
S28	6.859	0.00242	0.991
S90	4.114	0.00329	0.934

The fitting parameters a and b as presented in Table 3 provide useful information on the chloride ingress rate, which could be used to predict the chloride penetration depth h_{Cl} at later ages/exposure times of concrete samples.

$$K_{IC} = \frac{F_{max}\sqrt{a}}{RB\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{a}{R}}} Y_{I,BDCN}(a/R, \alpha_n) \xrightarrow{\text{Simplify}} K_{IC} = \frac{F_{max}}{B} \cdot C, \quad A (1)$$

$$B_{eff} = \frac{F_{max}}{K_{IC}}. \quad A (2)$$

$$B_{eff}^{S28} = \frac{F_{max}^{RO}}{K_{IC}^{Cl,S28}} \cdot C$$

$$B_{eff}^{RO} = \frac{F_{max}^{Cl,S28}}{K_{IC}^{RO}} \cdot C \quad A (3)$$

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